

NERSC Technical Report no. 431

**DATA DELIVERY CHAIN FOR PASSIVE
ACOUSTIC DATA LEVEL 2 PERCENTILES**

by

Frode Monsen

Florian Geyer

Torill Hamre

Espen Storheim

Tor I. Olaussen

30 November, 2023

	<p>Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC) Jahnebakken 3, N-5007 Bergen, Norway Phone: + 47 55 20 58 00 E-mail: post@nersc.no http://www.nersc.no</p>
---	--

<p>TITLE: Data delivery chain for passive acoustic data Level 2 Percentiles</p>	<p>REPORT IDENTIFICATION: NERSC Technical Report 431</p>
<p>CLIENT: Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC)</p>	<p>CONTRACT: “Smarte og Smidige dataleveringskjeder” (SIS SDL) (NERSC strategic institute project)</p>
<p>CLIENT REFERENCE:</p>	<p>AVAILABILITY: Public</p>
<p>INVESTIGATORS: Frode Monsen Florian Geyer Torill Hamre Espen Storheim Tor I. Olausen</p>	<p>AUTHORISATION:</p>
<p>DATE: 30 November, 2023</p>	
<p>SUMMARY: Observations and derived parameters from field experiments provide unique data about the state of the ocean. Such data are invaluable for improved understanding of processes and phenomena in the marine environment, and for correcting and validating model simulations. The majority of field experiments are conducted in short-term research projects with limited funding and strong focus on producing scientific publications. Therefore, it is essential to streamline and operationalize data delivery chains for in situ ocean data to increase the amount of scientific data available for research and use outside academia. This report describes a data delivery chain established to process, quality control, document, format and publish acoustic data percentile products in an open data repository. The developed delivery chain has been applied to acoustic data from the UNDER-ICE project and will be used to publish similar acoustic data percentile products from other research projects. This will make it less resource demanding to share this kind of acoustic data products with the scientific community and outside academia. Furthermore, the development will facilitate proper crediting to scientists, engineers, data managers and others that contribute to Open Science by making data available with standard metadata and data formats. Generic parts of the percentile delivery chain will be reused to develop cost-efficient delivery chains for other kinds of scientific data products. This will lessen the burden on research projects by providing templates and tools for preparing and publishing data in standard formats through open data repositories.</p>	

NERSC Technical Report Series. Report number 431.
 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11063825>

TABLE OF CONTENT:

1. Introduction	4
2. Passive acoustic data Level 2 Percentile product	4
2.1. The UNDER-ICE field experiment	5
2.2. Overview of processing	6
2.3. Examples of percentiles	7
3. Data and metadata format	7
3.1. File format, naming conventions and structure	7
3.2. Adherence to standards	8
3.3. Global (product) metadata	9
3.4. Parameter metadata	10
4. Workflow	11
4.1. Data offload and pre-processing	12
4.2. Data processing	12
4.3. Metadata compilation	12
4.4. Product generation	12
4.5. Product publication	13
5. Summary	14
6. References	14
Appendix A. Example Product NetCDF header	15

1. Introduction

Conducting field experiments and collecting in situ data in Arctic waters requires complex logistics, mature and robust instrumentation, as well as careful planning and implementation by highly skilled personnel in ocean observing. Field experiments are predominantly carried out in short term research projects, typically lasting 3-5 years. These projects usually have a strong focus on improving the understanding of ocean processes and phenomena, or on developing novel instruments for measuring important parameters more accurately or observing new parameters all together. With emphasis on scientific and technological development, the priority is publishing research papers and securing technical innovations to increase the chance of future funding. Since it is currently not rewarded, less weight is placed on securing that the collected data can be reused by researchers or outside academia.

Thus, while different observing platforms such as ocean moorings, buoys, and ships provide access to unique and multidisciplinary data, the data delivery chains for scientific data are not operationalized to offer fast formatting, structured storage, and easy access to data products. In earlier projects, among others [INTAROS](#) and [NMDC](#), new and better data structures and tools were developed by the Scientific Data Management Group (SDMG) and the Acoustic and Oceanography (AOG) research groups at NERSC. However, the data delivery chains were not sufficiently streamlined and automated. Streamlining of data delivery chains is an important contribution to Open Science, to enable data to be used optimally in research and management. Therefore the “Smarte og Smidige dataleveringskjeder” (SIS SDL) project was funded as a strategic institute project at NERSC. In this project, we will build on experience from [INTAROS](#), [SFI Smart Ocean](#), [UAK](#), [NMDC](#) and Ocean Data Dojo (Hamre et al., 2023a).

In addition to advancing the data structures, software tools and storage systems underpinning a streamlined data delivery chain for scientific ocean data products, it is crucial to motivate researchers to enter data into sustained data infrastructures. Unless the added value of data sharing is made visible and sharing data from research projects is included as a meriting criterion in academia, there is no incentive to put more effort into data sharing.

Data managers can support visibility by ensuring a data license and citation statement is included in the metadata, and by building support for citation counts and download counts into their data infrastructure. Licence metadata and a citation statement crediting all parties contributing to the generation and publishing of data are important parts of the metadata specification used in the data delivery chains for in situ ocean data at NERSC. This has been developed through several projects where data collectors and data managers have collaborated closely, combining their domain expertise to develop a metadata specification that captures the most important information about a data product and structuring this information in line with established metadata standards for the marine community (Hamre et al., 2023a). The close interaction between data collectors and data managers will be a central activity in the SIS SDL project to further improve and streamline data delivery chains for scientific data at NERSC.

The remainder of this report is organised as follows. Section 2 describes how the percentile data product is generated from acoustic recordings collected at five underwater ocean moorings in the Fram Strait. Section 3 gives an overview of the chosen file format and the metadata incorporated in the data files for facilitating search, access, and use through open protocols and software tools. Section 4 presents the main steps in the data delivery chain, from the measurements are offloaded from the instruments mounted on the moorings to the quality controlled and documented percentile data product is published using standard metadata and data formats in a long-term repository. Section 5 summaries the work carried out while developing the data delivery chain and outlines possible future use and extension.

2. Passive acoustic data Level 2 Percentile product

The level 2 data of the passive acoustics observations from the UNDER-ICE field experiment gives a statistical overview of the observed underwater soundscape. It consists of the 10th, 50th and 90th

percentile spectrum of each acoustic recording from the five UNDER-ICE moorings. The 50th percentile spectrum is equivalent to the median spectrum of the observed soundscape. Percentile spectra can be used to study the levels of ocean noise in relation to environmental conditions (wind, ice conditions). They describe the acoustic environment both in terms of its median state as well as the most quiet / most noisy 10% of the dataset. This can be used to describe the natural background environment in relation to e.g. planned man-made noises, or the typical noise levels of animal vocalisations.

2.1. The UNDER-ICE field experiment

The UNDER-ICE acoustic thermometry experiment was carried out in 2014-2016. For the experiment 5 moorings were deployed in Fram Strait between Svalbard and Greenland. The main objective was to remotely measure ocean temperatures along acoustic sections. For this purpose acoustic recordings were made, which can also be studied as passive acoustic data of the underwater soundscape. These passive acoustic data are described here. Each mooring consisted of a DSTAR control unit and 10 hydrophone modules (HMs) in an array configuration with a 9 m vertical distance between the HMs. The HMs recorded underwater sound every 3 hours for a duration of 130 seconds for each recording. The acoustic recordings discussed here are from hydrophones mounted on deep-water moorings, which has consequences for the processing and quality control.

Table 1. Mooring and hydrophone positions in UNDER-ICE experiment (from Geyer et al., 2021).

Mooring	Position	Hydrophone module depths (m)*	Water depth (m)
UI1	8.752E, 77.909N	467, 476, 494, 503, 512, 521, 530, 539, 548	1413
UI2	3.191E, 78.015N	336, 327, 318, 309, 300, 291, 282, 273, 264, 255	3040
UI3	4.224W, 78.166N	317, 308, 299, 290, 281, 272, 263, 254, 245, 236	2209
UI4	4.727W, 80.003N	313, 304, 295, 286, 277, 268, 259, 250, 241, 232	1419
UI5	5.1239E, 79.856N	565, 556, 547, 538, 529, 520, 511, 502, 493	1372

* Hydrophones with retrieved data only, 2 hydrophone modules were lost due to flooding

Figure 1. The UNDER-ICE acoustic thermometry experiment in Fram Strait (Figure from Geyer et al., 2021).

2.2. Overview of processing

Acoustic recordings from deep-water moorings can be influenced by noise from cable strumming. Therefore the processing included extensive quality check procedures to flag recordings which were possibly influenced by noise from cable strumming.

The processing of the acoustic data was done as follows (Geyer et al., 2021). The sample rate of the acoustic recordings is 1000 Hz. The measured raw signal in Volts was divided by the hydrophone sensitivity (-168 dB re 1 μ Pa) and the amplitude gain (12 dB) to calculate the measured pressure time series in μ Pa for each 130 s long recording. Acoustic spectrograms were calculated using a Hanning window with a length of 128 data points and a 50% overlap (Level 1 data). For each recording percentile spectra for the 10th, 50th and 90th percentile were calculated (Level 2 data, presented here). In addition, the 1st and 99th percentile spectra were calculated for quality control and testing purposes only, they are not part of the dataset for publication.

The quality evaluation of the passive acoustic data was done in two steps. In the first step, oversaturated recordings were identified and marked. The second step tried to identify instances of mooring self-noise from cable strumming by using vertical mooring motion data. Figure 3 shows how periods of high noise levels measured by an UNDER-ICE hydrophone module coincide with periods of mooring pushdown events by ocean currents. This correspondence was used to find threshold values of vertical mooring displacement below which the influence of cable strumming on the acoustic recording is negligible. Different thresholds were tested and compared to determine the motion threshold for each hydrophone module. Figure 4 shows an example of such a comparison. For each hydrophone module the percentile spectra for the 1st, 10th, 50th, 90th and 99th percentile were plotted for different threshold values of vertical mooring displacement (Figure 4). Strumming noise was identifiable by spectral lines and by increased noise levels at the lowest frequencies. The threshold was chosen such that no spectral lines were present at the 90th percentile. In addition, the noise levels using the chosen threshold had to be similar to the noise levels that would have resulted from choosing a smaller threshold.

Figure 2. Flow diagram for UNDER-ICE level 2 data processing, coloured outlines denote the main parts of the processing chain. Red: processing of acoustic data and calculation of percentile spectra. Yellow: setting thresholds for mooring motion, calculate quality flags. Green: collecting acoustic data, quality flags and metadata and save as NetCDF file (Figure from Geyer et al., 2021).

2.3. Examples of percentiles

Percentiles are a good way to summarise the main statistical properties of a dataset with a skewed, non-gaussian distribution. Therefore percentile spectra were chosen as the level 2 data product for the UNDER-ICE passive recordings. For each recording, there is one set of three percentile spectra for the 10th, 50th and 90th percentile spectrum (Geyer et al., 2021). The 50th percentile is equivalent to a median spectrum. The dataset also contains a quality flag for each of the recordings, denoting if the recording was influenced by mooring self-noise from cable strumming. The definitions of the quality flag values follow standards from NMDC (Hamre et al. 2017). Quality flag 2 denotes “probably good data”, while quality flag 4 denotes “bad data, cable strumming”. Figure 3 shows an example of two such spectra with quality flags 2 and 4, respectively.

Figure 3. Percentile spectra of two recordings from the same hydrophone module (HM 543, mooring UI5). The recording on the left panel was assigned quality flag 4 (bad data / cable strumming). The recording on the right panel was assigned quality flag 2 (probably good data). The effects of the cable strumming are visible at all plotted percentiles and include both spectral lines and a general increase of the measured noise levels. (Figure from Geyer et al., 2021)

The amount of data which is flagged as influenced by cable strumming (quality flag 4, bad data) differs strongly between moorings, depending on the strength of the ocean currents at the different mooring Locations. Hardly any data from mooring UI4 is labelled with quality flag 4, about 90% of the recordings from moorings UI1, UI3, and UI5 are influenced by cable strumming and therefore assigned quality flag 4. At mooring UI2 the vertical mooring positioning proved to be unreliable resulting in spikes and periods of wrong mooring depth estimates. Therefore, no vertical mooring displacement thresholds could be defined for UI2 and all recordings from UI2 had to be flagged with quality flag 4.

3. Data and metadata format

This section describes how the percentile data product is formatted using leading standards for scientific metadata and data. Adopting standards enables data to be shared and reused by the wider research community and beyond academia (e.g. in the public sector and in private companies).

3.1. File format, naming conventions and structure

NetCDF (Network Common Data Form) is a community standard for storing and sharing scientific data with multiple parameters and dimensions. The NetCDF format is machine-independent and can

be created, accessed, and shared across multiple computer platforms, using software libraries, tools and frameworks provided by providers with long-term support, such as Unidata (Unidata, 2023a). Benefits of using NetCDF include, among others:

- Metadata (i.e., description of the data) can be included in the NetCDF data file. This makes the data file *Self-Describing*.
- NetCDF is a *Portable* data format. This means a NetCDF file generated on a specific computer platform (e.g., Linux) can be read and interpreted by software running on different platforms (e.g., Mac or Windows).
- NetCDF is *Scalable*, meaning smaller parts (subsets) of large datasets can be accessed efficiently using the standard NetCDF interfaces. These interfaces allow access from remote data servers. Thus, a program running on a computer with less disk space can extract just the part of a dataset needed for the task at hand.
- Data can be *appended* to a properly structured NetCDF file without copying the datafile or redefining its structure. Metadata can also be added to an existing NetCDF file.
- Several software clients (one writer, multiple readers) can access a given NetCDF file at the same time. I.e. a NetCDF file is *Sharable* between several software tools.
- NetCDF is *backwards-compatible*. This means data stored in earlier versions of the NetCDF format will be supported by current and future versions of the software from Unidata and other providers using the Unidata NetCDF libraries.

The percentile product is generated from acoustic recordings from a fixed ocean mooring (see sec.2). Percentiles for a mooring is stored in a NetCDF file. The filenames consist of 7 parts;

- The area and project for which the measurements were made. (ARCTIC_UNDERICE_)
- The mooring name where the data is taken. (UI5_)
- The start date for the measurements, formatted as YYYYMMDD. (20140908-)
- The end date for the measurements, formatted as YYYYMMDD. (20160306_)
- Type of measurements. (ambientnoise)
- Level of data processing done. (L2)
- Filetype, the standard extension for NetCDF files. (.nc)

The files are structured with global administrative attributes at the root (global metadata), and everything else in a group named STAR_<location/station name>. Inside the group there are group attributes (group metadata) that are more technically oriented than the global data, variables, attributes for the variables, all the variable values, and dimensions.

3.2. Adherence to standards

NetCDF files for the percentile data product follow the standard “Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Conventions” (Eaton et al., 2011) for describing the variables in the dataset. The purpose of the CF conventions is to require conforming datasets to contain sufficient metadata that they are self-describing in the sense that each variable in the file has an associated description of what it represents.

CF conventions also recommend a few attributes that are common for all the variables and describe the whole dataset (global attributes), but a more complete standard for global attributes used is “Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD)” (ESIP, 2020). The attributes recommended by ACDD describe a NetCDF file for discovery systems such as Digital Libraries, THREDDS and other tools, and for exporting the datasets to Dublin core, ISO 19115 and other metadata formats.

In addition to these standards, we have also utilised the OceanSITES metadata conventions” (OceanSITES, 2010) and the “MET Norway Metadata Format (MMD)” specification. The purpose of

the OceanSITES metadata specification is to make data easy to discover, and to interpret and use appropriately. MMD is made to document datasets in order to make them findable. In this it supports information elements of Findable, Accessible, and Reusable from the FAIR guiding principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

3.3. Global (product) metadata

Global metadata are several attributes that describe the origin and content of the data. These files follow the standards ACDD 1.3 (ESIP, 2020), and CF 1.6 (Eaton et al., 2011), but do not include all the recommended attributes. Some of the key attributes are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Global metadata for the percentile data product.

Attribute	Convention	Description
data_set_language	Rosetta	Which language is the dataset written in
Conventions	ACDD, CF	A list of the conventions followed by the dataset
id	ACDD, CF	A unique identifier for each dataset. This is often the same as the filename. The combination of naming_authority and id should be globally unique.
naming_authority	ACDD	The organisation that provides the initial id (see above) for the dataset. Reverse-DNS naming is used for the naming authority.
title	ACDD, CF	A short phrase or sentence describing the dataset.
geospatial_lat, geospatial_lon, geospatial_lat_units, geospatial_lon_units	ACDD	The location where the measurements were performed.
iso_topic_category	INSPIRE	Part of INTAROS metadata specification (Hamre et al., 2021) and used by MET Norway for filtering data when searching for relevant datasets. Accepted values are listed here: https://htmlpreview.github.io/?https://github.com/metno/mmd/blob/master/doc/mmd-specification.html#iso-topic-categories
license	ACDD	Provides the URL to the specific license that restricts the use of the datafile.
citation	OceanSITES, MMD	Statement to be used when citing the dataset in publications.
acknowledgement	ACDD	A place to acknowledge various types of support for the project that produced the dataset.
summary	ACDD	A paragraph describing the dataset, analogous to an abstract for a paper.
keywords_vocabulary	ACDD	This is the unique name or identifier of the vocabulary from which keywords are taken.
keywords	ACDD	A comma-separated list of key words and/or

		phrases
time_coverage_start, time_coverage_end	ACDD	The first and last timestamp in the dataset.
history	ACDD, CF	Describes the processes/transformations used to create this data, what and when.
platform	ACDD	Name of the platform(s) that supported the sensor data used to create this data set or product.
funding_agency	Smart Ocean	Name of body funding the project(s). If multiple projects separate by comma.
project_lead, project_lead_email	Smart Ocean	Name and email of person leading the project(s). If multiple projects separate by comma.
principal_investigator, principal_investigator_email	OceanSITES	Name and e-mail address of principal investigator of the project(s).
investigator, investigator_email	Smart Ocean	Name and affiliation, and e-mail address of the responsible investigator.
cruise_responsible, cruise_responsible_email	INTAROS	Principle Investigator(s) of the cruise(s), and their organisation. Email address of the responsible investigator.
contributor_name, contributor_role, contributor_email	ACDD	The name, role and e-mail address of any individuals, projects, or institutions that contributed to the creation of this data.
publisher_name, publisher_email, publisher_url	ACDD	The name of the organisation, e-mail address and website for the organisation responsible for publishing the data file or product to users, with its current metadata and format.
institution	CF	Name of the organisation where the original data was produced.
data_assembly_center	OceanSITES	Data Assembly Center (DAC) in charge of this data file.
cdm_data_type	ACDD	The data type as understood by THREDDS. It is similar, but can differ from the 'featureType' attribute.
processing_level	ACDD	A textual description of the processing (or quality control) level of the data.

3.4. Parameter metadata

Variables in the NetCDF files represent the measured and calculated values described in section 2. The variables have their own attributes, and the number of values in a variable is defined by dimensions. Each dimension must have a 1 dimensional variable that sets the size of that dimension, and has the same name as the dimension.

Dimensions used here are :

- **time**: the number of times measurements were taken
- **frequency**: the number of frequencies that measurements were taken at.
- **percentile**: the number of percentiles used in calculations.
- **hydrophone**: the number of hydrophones represented in the file.

The attributes used by most of the variables are :

- **long_name**: a free text string that works as a description of the variable
- **standard_name**: a short standardised description of the variable, adheres to the standard name list specified in the global attribute 'standard_name_vocabulary'. Not all variables have a standard name in a vocabulary.
- **units**: specify what unit the values of the variable are recorded in.
- **valid_range**: the maximum and minimum value that is valid for the variable.
- **coverage_content_type**: An ISO 19115-1 code to indicate the source of the data.
- **comments**: extra information about the variable that does not fit in the cf standard attributes.

The variables in these files are:

- **time**: decimal numbers given in the number of days since 1. Jan 0001 at midnight. The attribute **calendar** specifies how days are counted.
- **frequency**: Frequency of the sound measured. Decimal number in Hz.
- **percentile**: Identifies the percentiles in use.
- **hydrophone**: Identifies the hydrophone. The attribute **cf-role** identifies this variable as the identifier for the time series data.
- **snd_pressure**: 4 dimensional data structure of decimal numbers that represents the measured sound pressure in water in Pascal along all of the dimensions named above.
- **snd_power**: The ocean sound level is given as the spectral power in dB for the same dimensions as **snd_pressure**.
- **snd_qc**: Quality flag for each measurement. The attribute **flag_values** specifies what values the flag can have, and the attribute **flag_meanings** describes the meaning of each value.

4. Workflow

This section describes the data delivery chain for the Passive acoustic data Level 2 Percentile product derived from acoustic recordings made by the Hydrophone Modules (HM) on the moorings. The steps in the processing chain (Figure 4) are described below.

Figure 4. Illustration of the data delivery chain for the passive acoustic data level 2 percentile product.

4.1. Data offload and pre-processing

The first part is to offload the data from the instruments, the raw data is in NetCDF format. The data offload is done using the HM support computers, which processes the raw data on the SD-cards and generates the different NetCDF files including the acoustic receptions in the file format `rcv_<timestamp>.nc`.

The raw acoustic data must be converted into a pressure time series in μPa as described in chapter 2.2. These pressure series form the pre-processed acoustic data and are stored as one Matlab data file (.mat) per hydrophone module.

4.2. Data processing

A script similar to the one for preprocessing calculates spectrograms from the pressure time series and then calculates the percentile spectra for each acoustic spectrum. The details are again described in section 2.2. The results are stored as one Matlab data file (.mat) per hydrophone module.

The main part of the processing consists of the quality control of the data, which is needed to set a quality control flag variable for each recording. As described in section 2.2, the quality control consists of two steps. The first step identifies overloaded data by a simple threshold comparison. The results of this step are saved as Matlab data files. The second step uses mooring motion data and the correspondence between mooring motion and (unwanted) cable strumming noise to identify which recordings were likely influenced by cable strumming. For this step mooring motion data is needed as Matlab data files (.mat). These files stem from the acoustic tomography processing of the mooring data, which is not described here. The mooring motion, which contains the motion of the STAR control unit is first converted to a hydrophone displacement for each hydrophone module. These are saved as Matlab data files (.mat). A plotting program is then used to manually identify a motion threshold for each hydrophone module. This threshold, which has to be decided is saved manually by the person doing the processing, is then hardcoded in a special Matlab subscript file (`mMotion_threshold.m`). A last step then collects all the generated quality control information and saves the resulting quality control decision in a Matlab data file (.mat). There is one file per mooring, which contains the quality control summary for all hydrophone modules on this mooring.

A last processing step collects both the processed data, the quality control variable and most of the needed Metadata and saves them in NetCDF format (.nc). There is one NetCDF file for each mooring containing the information from all hydrophone modules on this mooring.

4.3. Metadata compilation

A significant amount of metadata is necessary in the preparation of the data for publishing. There are global metadata attributes, which are describing the projects on a high-level, and variable attributes, where information about the specific variables are listed. The global metadata is specified by the scientist(s) generating the percentile data product using a PDF form developed by the Scientific Data Management Group (SDMG) at NERSC. The metadata is checked by the scientist responsible for the research project or cruise, and by SMDG member(s) before being ingested in the NetCDF data file.

4.4. Product generation

Variable attributes

Most of the variable attributes are related to the variables themselves, not the specific data on the mooring. For the percentile data, a set of CF attributes has been identified. These variable attributes can be used again when generating percentile data products in other projects, e.g. CAATEX and HiAOOS.

Global attributes

SDMG has prepared a PDF form which contains input fields for the global attributes in table 2. The data from this form is semi-automatically added to the NetCDF files using a Python script. The location of the PDF forms and NetCDF files are entered into a configuration file.

4.5. Product publication

The final step in the data delivery chain is publishing the percentile data product in NMDC. For this purpose we use community standard software THREDDS Data Server (Unidata, 2023b) and GeoNetwork (OSGF, 2023). THREDDS makes the data product available online through standard protocols such as [OPeNDAP](#) and [HTTPS](#).

We have created a semi-automatic workflow with the open source workflow manager Apache Airflow (<https://airflow.apache.org/>) to publish the percentile data to THREDDS. This process uses a combination of Python and Bash scripts that can be initialised through two configuration files. The metadata is read directly from the NetCDF files. The location of the files and other information not available in the NetCDF files are entered in the configuration files. The result of this is a well-formed catalog.xml file that is used directly on the THREDDS server. This file describes the percentile data files and how to access them through the THREDDS server.

An ISO 19139 compliant metadata record is then created with a description of the data product made available through THREDDS. GeoNetwork makes these metadata available to the central [NMDC portal](#), which provides a common entry point to all datasets in the NMDC data infrastructure. The NMDC metadata contains key elements such as (product) title, author, license, citation, and links to data access. Fig.5 shows the landing page for the percentile dataset described in this report.

Seamless access to Norwegian marine data

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center
https://doi.org/doi:10.21335/NMDC-NERSC-1247352671

UNDERICE: Ambient noise in water _ 08/09/2014-06/03/2016

Recommended citation:
Hanne Sagen (Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center) Florian Geyer (Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center) Espen Storheim (Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center) Frode Monsen (Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center) Tor Olausen (Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center) Torill Hamre (Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center) (2023) UNDERICE: Ambient noise in water _ 08/09/2014-06/03/2016
https://doi.org/doi:10.21335/NMDC-NERSC-1247352671

To cite this dataset use the following:
[Text citation](#)

Usage :
The user must display the following citation in any publication or product using this dataset:
"Florian Geyer; Hanne Sagen; Espen Storheim; Frode Monsen; Tor I. Olausen; Torill Hamre (2023). UNDER-ICE: Arctic Ocean Under Melting Ice - Ambient noise in water 08/09/2014-06/03/2016." The user should refer to the following publication for the data processing: Florian Geyer; Hanne Sagen; Espen Storheim, 2021. A dataset of underwater passive acoustic recordings from av2-year mooring deployment in Fram Strait (UNDER-ICE), Proc. Mtgs. Acoust 44, 070034 (2021), https://doi.org/10.1121/2.0001507

Abstract
This dataset is based on acoustic recordings from five moorings deployed during the UNDER-ICE experiment in the Fram Strait. The U11 mooring carried 8 hydrophones: HM501 (467m), HM502 (476m), HM504 (494m), HM505 (503m), HM506 (512m), HM507 (521m), HM509 (530m), HM310 (539m). A total of 8188 recordings were obtained from each hydrophone every 3 hours from Sep 2014 - Jan 2016. The U12 mooring carried 10 hydrophones: HM511 (336m), HM512 (327m), HM513 (318m), HM514 (309m), HM515 (300m), HM516 (291m), HM517 (282m), HM518 (273m), HM519 (264m), HM320 (255m). A total of 4358 recordings were obtained from each hydrophone every 3 hours from Sep 2014 - Jan 2016. The U13 mooring carried 10 hydrophones: HM521 (317m), HM522 (308m), HM523 (299m), HM524 (290m), HM525 (281m), HM526 (272m), HM527 (263m), HM528 (254m), HM529 (245m), HM330 (236m). A total of 8188 recordings were obtained from each hydrophone every 3 hours from Sep 2014 - Jan 2016. The U14 mooring carried 10 hydrophones: HM531 (313m), HM532 (304m), HM533 (295m), HM534 (286m), HM535 (277m), HM536 (268m), HM537 (259m), HM538 (250m), HM539 (241m), HM340 (232). A total of 8189 recordings were obtained from each hydrophone every 3 hours from Sep 2014 - Jan 2016. The U15 mooring carried 9 hydrophones: HM542 (565m), HM543 (556m), HM544 (547m), HM545 (538m), HM546 (529m), HM547 (520m), HM548 (511m), HM549 (502m), HM550 (493m). A total of 4359 recordings were obtained from each hydrophone every 3 hours from Sep 2014 - Mar 2016. Each acoustic recording covered 130 s with sampling rate 1000Hz. 10-, 50- and 90- percentiles of sound pressure and power were calculated for each reception using 50 % overlapping Hanning window with a window length of 1024 samples. The units for sound pressure is Pa. The unit for power (ocean sound level) is dB re uPa2 Hz-1. Noise by cable strumming is included. The

Data downloads

Type	Description	URL
GET DATA	Description	https://thredds.nersc.no/thredds/fileServer/HIAOOS/ARCTIC_UNDERICE_UI1_20140906-20160131_ambientnoiseL2/ARCTIC_UNDERICE_UI1_20140906-20160131_ambientnoiseL2.nc
GET DATA	Description	https://thredds.nersc.no/thredds/fileServer/HIAOOS/ARCTIC_UNDERICE_UI1_20140906-20160131_ambientnoiseL2/ARCTIC_UNDERICE_UI2_20140902-20160229_ambientnoiseL2.nc
GET DATA	Description	https://thredds.nersc.no/thredds/fileServer/HIAOOS/ARCTIC_UNDERICE_UI1_20140906-20160131_ambientnoiseL2/ARCTIC_UNDERICE_UI3_20140905-20160130_ambientnoiseL2.nc
GET DATA	Description	https://thredds.nersc.no/thredds/fileServer/HIAOOS/ARCTIC_UNDERICE_UI1_20140906-20160131_ambientnoiseL2/ARCTIC_UNDERICE_UI4_20140903-20160128_ambientnoiseL2.nc
GET DATA	Description	https://thredds.nersc.no/thredds/fileServer/HIAOOS/ARCTIC_UNDERICE_UI1_20140906-20160131_ambientnoiseL2/ARCTIC_UNDERICE_UI5_20140908-20160306_ambientnoiseL2.nc

Figure 5. Landing page for the percentile dataset
(<https://doi.org/doi:10.21335/NMDC-NERSC-1247352671>).

5. Summary

This report has described the data delivery chain established for the passive acoustic data Level 2 Percentile product at NERSC. The delivery chain runs from acoustic recordings measured at an ocean mooring are offloaded to an inhouse computer to the publication of the quality controlled and documented data production in an open data infrastructure. The percentile product is based on data collected from five ocean moorings deployed in the Fram Strait between September 2014 to February 2015 as part of the RCN UNDER-ICE project. An overview of the processing and examples of percentile spectra are presented, along with a short description of the UNDER-ICE field experiment. This is followed by the definition of a standard-compliant data format with ample metadata to document the data product, and support search and access in the NMDC data infrastructure. The chosen format is based on community standards for data and metadata, including NetCDF, CF and ACDD, adapted and extended to give credit to funding agencies, project and coordination personnel, and all staff that has contributed to the collection, processing, and/or publication of the product. Each step in the workflow for the delivery chain is described, culminating with the data product being published with a unique identifier, data license, acknowledgement and citation statements to ensure proper credit can be given by data consumers.

6. References

- Eaton, Brian, Jonathan Gregory, Bob Drach, Karl Taylor, Steve Hankin, John Caron, Rich Signell, Phil Bentley, Greg Rappa, Heinke Höck, Alison Pamment, Martin Jukes, 2011. CF convention, Version 1.6, 5 December, 2011. <http://cfconventions.org/> (accessed 7 July 2023).
- ESIP. 2020. Attribute Convention for Data Discovery 1-3. https://wiki.esipfed.org/Attribute_Convention_for_Data_Discovery_1-3 (accessed 7 July 2023).
- Geyer, Florian, Sagen, Hanne, and Espen Storheim; A dataset of underwater passive acoustic recordings from a 2-year mooring deployment in Fram Strait (UNDER-ICE). Proc. Mtgs. Acoust 20 June 2021; 44 (1): 070034. <https://doi.org/10.1121/2.0001507>
- Hamre, Torill, Monsen, Frode, Storheim, Espen, Sagen, Hanne, Olausson, Tor I., Sandven, Stein, 2023b. Smart Ocean: Metadata and data formats for oceanographic and acoustic data products from field experiments in Bjørnafjorden and Langenuen. NERSC Technical Report 429.
- Hamre, Torill and Lara Ferrighi, 2023a. Ocean Data Dojo – Report from workshops on marine data delivery chains in Svalbard. NERSC Technical Report no. 427.
- Hamre, Torill, Sagen, Hanne, Sandven, Stein, Danielsen, Finn, Ottersen, Geir, Beszczynska-Moller, Agnieszka, Morvik, Arnfinn, Yamakawa, Asuka, Schewe, Ingo, & Enghoff, Martin. (2021). Deliverable 1.8 Data Management Plan V2. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7015039>
- Hamre, Torill, Godøy, Øystein, Ringheim, Sjur Lid, Tronstad, Stein, Sagen, Helge, Fjellheim, Kjetil, Østerhus. Svein, Krogstad, Morten, Lepland, Aave, Nordlund, Nina, Kristiansen, Svein, Vang, Roald, Karud, Jan, Valland, Nils, and Pfeil, Benjamin, 2017. D3.1 – Definition of data formats and metadata structure. NERSC Technical Report 383.
- OceanSITES, 2010. OceanSITES User’s Manual NetCDF Conventions and Reference Tables. Version 1.2. June 29, 2010.
- Open Source Geospatial Foundation (OSGF), 2023. GeoNetwork. <https://geonetwork-opensource.org/>
- Unidata, 2023a. Network Common Data Form (NetCDF). <https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/>
- Unidata, 2023b. Thredds Data Server, Version 5.4. TDS: doi:10.5065/D6N014KG <https://doi.org/10.5065/D6N014KG>
- Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- Yamakawa, A., Dushaw, B., Sagen, H. and T. Hamre (2019). Data standardization for long-term underwater acoustic observation - Ocean temperature and ambient noise data in Fram Strait, NERSC Technical Report No. 391, Version 1.0, Revised March 2019.

Appendix A. Example Product NetCDF header

```
netcdf ARCTIC_UNDERICE_UI5_20140908-20160306_ambientnoiseL2 {  
  
  // global attributes:  
  :cmd_data_type = "point, timeSeries" ;  
  :date_created = "2023-07-13T15:22:42Z" ;  
  :featureType = "timeSeries" ;  
  :geospatial_lat = 79.856 ;  
  :geospatial_lat_units = "degree_north" ;  
  :geospatial_lon = 5.1239 ;  
  :geospatial_lon_units = "degree_east" ;  
  :institution = "Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC)" ;  
  :iso_topic_category = "oceans" ;  
  :keywords_vocabulary = "GCMD Science Keywords" ;  
  :platform_detail = "1 DSTAR(s) were installed in the platform. Each DSTAR controlled up to 10  
hydrophones." ;  
  :publisher_email = "datamanager@nersc.no" ;  
  :standard_name_vocabulary = "CF Standard Name version 57" ;  
  :time_coverage_duration = "P545D" ;  
  :time_coverage_end = "2016-03-06T15:02:06Z" ;  
  :time_coverage_resolution = "P3H" ;  
  :time_coverage_start = "2014-09-08T21:02:06Z" ;  
  :title = "UNDERICE: Ambient noise in water _ 08/09/2014-06/03/2016" ;  
  :Conventions = "CF-1.6, ACDD-1.3" ;  
  :date_modified = "2023-07-14T11:29:44+0200" ;  
  :history = "2023-07-13T15:22:42Z creation; 2023-07-14T11:29:44+0200 metadata updated" ;  
  :id = "ARCTIC_UNDERICE_UI5_20140908-20160306_ambientnoiseL2" ;  
  :contributor_email = "Hanne.Sagen@nersc.no; Florian.Geyer@nersc.no; Espen.Storheim@nersc.no;  
Frode.Monsen@nersc.no; Tor.Olaussen@nersc.no; Torill.Hamre@nersc.no" ;  
  :contributor_name = "Hanne Sagen; Florian Geyer; Espen Storheim; Frode Monsen; Tor I. Olaussen;  
Torill Hamre" ;  
  :contributor_role = "Principal investigator and Data collection; Data collection, Processing  
and Formatting; Data collection; Data curation; Publishing data; Data manager" ;  
  :data_assembly_center = "NERSC" ;  
  :keywords = "EARTH SCIENCE, OCEANS, OCEAN ACOUSTICS, AMBIENT NOISE" ;  
  :license = "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/. Users must include the  
acknowledgement and citation for these data." ;  
  :naming_authority = "no.nersc.under-ice" ;  
  :platform = "UI5" ;  
  :project = "UNDER-ICE (RCN project no. 226373)" ;  
  :publisher_name = "Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center" ;  
  :publisher_url = "https://www.nersc.no/" ;  
  :source = "ocean mooring observation" ;  
  :summary = "This mooring is part of the UNDER-ICE experiment in the Fram Strait. The mooring  
carried 9 hydrophones: HM542 (565m), HM543 (556m), HM544 (547m), HM545 (538m), HM546 (529m), HM547  
(520m), HM548 (511m), HM549 (502m), HM550 (493m). A total of 4359 recordings were obtained from each  
hydrophone every 3 hours from Sep 2014 - Mar 2016. Each acoustic recording covered 130 s with sampling  
rate 1000Hz. 10-, 50- and 90- percentiles of sound pressure and power were calculated for each  
reception using 50 % overlapping Hanning window with a window length of 1024 samples. The units for  
sound pressure is Pa. The unit for power (ocean sound level) is dB re uPa2 Hz-1. Noise by cable  
strumming is included. The processing is described in Geyer et al. 2021  
https://doi.org/10.1121/2.0001507. " ;  
  :processing_level = "Level 2 (Data verified against model or other contextual information)" ;  
  :publisher_type = "institution" ;  
  :publisher_institution = "Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center" ;  
  :project_id = "226373" ;  
  :funding_agency = "The Research Council of Norway (RCN)" ;  
  :project_lead = "Hanne Sagen, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center" ;  
  :project_lead_email = "Hanne.Sagen@nersc.no" ;  
  :principal_investigator = "Hanne Sagen, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center" ;  
  :principal_investigator_email = "hanne.sagen@nersc.no" ;  
  :investigator = "Florian Geyer, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center" ;  
  :investigator_email = "florian.geyer@nersc.no" ;  
  :cruise_id = "KV Svalbard 2016" ;  
  :cruise_responsible = "Hanne Sagen, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center" ;  
  :cruise_responsible_email = "Hanne.Sagen@nersc.no" ;  
  :data_set_language = "english" ;  
  :citation = "The user must display the following citation in any publication or product using  
this dataset: \r\n\"Florian Geyer; Hanne Sagen; Espen Storheim; Frode Monsen; Tor I. Olaussen; Torill  
Hamre (2023). UNDER-ICE: Arctic Ocean Under Melting Ice - Ambient noise in water  
08/09/2014-06/03/2016\". \r\nThe user should refer to the following publication for the data
```

```

processing:\rFlorian Geyer; Hanne Sagen; Espen Storheim, 2021. A dataset of underwater passive acoustic
recordings from a\r2-year mooring deployment in Fram Strait (UNDER-ICE), Proc. Mtgs. Acoust 44, 070034
(2021), https://doi.org/10.1121/2.0001507 ;
:acknowledgement = "Data were collected in the RCN project UNDER-ICE (project no. 226373),
processed, quality controlled, and formatted in the HORIZON 2020 project INTAROS (grant agreement no.
727890 ), and published with metadata in the NERSC Strategic Institute Project SDL (Smarte og smidige
dataleveringskjeder). Special thanks to the Norwegian Coast Guard for allocating ship time with KV
Svalbard for UNDER-ICE mooring deployment and recovery.\" " ;
:area = "Fram Strait, Arctic Ocean" ;
group: STAR_UI5 {
  dimensions:
    time = 4359 ;
    frequency = 513 ;
    percentile = 3 ;
    hydrophone = 9 ;
  variables:
    double time(time) ;
      time:calendar = "gregorian" ;
      time:long_name = "time" ;
      time:standard_name = "time" ;
      time:units = "days since 1-1-1 0:0:0" ;
      time:valid_range = 735850.876458333, 736395.626458333 ;
    double frequency(frequency) ;
      frequency:frequency_resolution = 0.9747 ;
      frequency:long_name = "sound_frequency" ;
      frequency:standard_name = "sound_frequency" ;
      frequency:units = "Hz" ;
      frequency:valid_range = 0., 1000. ;
    float percentile(percentile) ;
      percentile:comments = "10- 50- and 90- percentiles are common for use." ;
      percentile:long_name = "percentile" ;
      percentile:units = "Percent" ;
      percentile:valid_range = 0., 100. ;
    double hydrophone(hydrophone) ;
      hydrophone:comments = "hydrophone ID in the STAR." ;
      hydrophone:long_name = "hydrophone_ID" ;
      hydrophone:standard_name = "platform_name" ;
      hydrophone:cf_role = "timeseries_id" ;
      hydrophone:units = "1" ;
    float snd_pressure(hydrophone, percentile, time, frequency) ;
      snd_pressure:coverage_content_type = "physicalMeasurement" ;
      snd_pressure:long_name = "10-, 50-, 90-percentiles_sound_pressure_in_water" ;
      snd_pressure:standard_name = "sound_pressure_in_water" ;
      snd_pressure:units = "Pa" ;
      snd_pressure:valid_range = 2979.60703167645, 2119281665.70312 ;
    float snd_power(hydrophone, percentile, time, frequency) ;
      snd_power:comments = "The ocean sound level is given as the spectral power in dB re 1
\\muPa^2 Hz^{-1}" ;
      snd_power:coverage_content_type = "physicalMeasurement" ;
      snd_power:long_name = "10-, 50-, 90-percentiles_ocean_sound_in_level" ;
      snd_power:units = "dB" ;
      snd_power:valid_range = 19.79752952172, 139.848423232734 ;
    byte snd_qc(hydrophone, time) ;
      snd_qc:comments = "Mechanical noise was detected by the hydrophone displacement with
threshold 6.0, 6.0, 6.0, 6.0, 6.0, 6.0, 6.0, 6.0, 5.0 m. 2 stands for recording without mechanical
noise. 4 means recording incl. mechanical / electronic noise. When hydrophone displacement information
is missing, the corresponding recording takes flag_value 0." ;
      snd_qc:coverage_content_type = "qualityInformation" ;
      snd_qc:flag_meanings = "No_QC_was_performed Good_data Probably_good_data
Bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable Bad_data Value_changed" ;
      snd_qc:long_name = "quality_flag" ;
      snd_qc:quality_control_indicator_conventions = "Table 2 in OceanSITES Data Format
Reference Manual" ;
      snd_qc:standard_name = "status_flag" ;
      snd_qc:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b ;

  // group attributes:
  :acoustic_sampling_end_date = "2016-03-06T15:02:06Z" ;
  :acoustic_sampling_start_date = "2014-09-08T21:02:06Z" ;
  :acoustic_sampling_temporal_resolution = "P3H" ;
  :geospatial_vertical_positive = "down" ;
  :geospatial_vertical_units = "EPSG:5831" ;
  :hydrophone_id = 542., 543., 544., 545., 546., 547., 548., 549., 550. ;
  :hydrophone_type = "pressure sensor" ;

```

```

      :instrument = "hydrophone_pressure_sensor, AD_converter" ;
      :instrument_id = "STAR_S/N_" ;
      :instrument_other_info = "Distributed Simple Tomographic Acoustic Receiver (STAR) /10
hydrophone modules developed by Scripps Institution of Oceanography" ;
      :nominal_geospatial_vertical_depth = "565.0 556.0 547.0 538.0 529.0 520.0 511.0 502.0 493.0 " ;
      :nominal_geospatial_vertical_depth_unit = "m" ;
      :processing_level = "Data verified against model or other contextual information" ;
      :processing_level_conventions = "Table.3 in OceanSITES Data Format Reference Manual" ;
      :sample_rate = 1000. ;
      :summary = "Passive acoustic data were recorded with 9 hydrophone(s) and a total of 4359
receptions were obtained from each hydrophone. Each observed acoustic data records 130 s with sampling
rate 1000Hz.10-, 50- and 90- percentiles of sound pressure and power were calculated for each reception
using 50 % overlapping Hanning window with a window length of 1024 samples.The units for sound pressure
is Pa. The unit for power (ocean sound level) is dB re microPa2 Hz-1. Noise by cable strumming is
included." ;
      data:

      hydrophone = 542, 543, 544, 545, 546, 547, 548, 549, 550 ;
    } // group STAR_UI5
  }

```